

MYOCARDITIS AND PERICARDITIS

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ABSTRACT

Myocarditis (myo-muscle, card-heart, itis-inflammation) is myocardial inflammation not caused by any secondary infection or disease. At the same time, pericarditis (around the heart) is inflammation in the pericardium, which is the outer covering of the heart. Myocarditis or pericarditis, also known as myopericarditis, is an inflammatory disease of the myocardium or the pericardial sac. They also show myocyte necrosis, which is nonischemic. There are varieties of signs and symptoms in myocarditis and pericarditis, such as acute heart failure, dilated chronic cardiomyopathy, and possibly even death. However, it is undetected in disease and adverse drug and vaccine reactions in critical conditions.

Most MCP is due to viral causes but can also be due to microbial pathogenesis. Toxic myocarditis (reversible) occurs in the case of diphtheria, and in some cases, when autoimmune mechanisms may contribute, it can be due to infective endocarditis. Show growing organisms like, chlamydia and trypanosome infection in Chagas disease can cause chronic myocarditis.

Pericarditis causes an acute illness and complicates rheumatic renal or malignant disease. We suggest echocardiography to ensure pericardial involvement in noncardiac conditions. We can observe pericardial pain and sometimes pericardial friction, and in ECG, we can also see ST-segment elevation.

Keywords: myocarditis, pericarditis, myopericarditis, immunization.

INTRODUCTION

Definition

Myocarditis is a condition in which autoimmune inflammation of the heart mainly affects children and adults. The leading common cause is a viral infection. However, in etiology, we included bacterial and protozoal infections, toxins, and reactions to some drugs. Myocarditis or pericarditis is also known as myopericarditis, an inflammatory disease of the myocardium or the pericardial sac. They also show myocyte necrosis, which is nonischemic. Therefore, acute injuries here can lead to myocyte damage, which can initiate the humoral immune system. This leads to severe inflammation.

Pericarditis

Pericarditis is inflammation in the pericardial sac. This can be associated with pericardial syndromes. In this study, we noticed increased fluid accumulation within the sac, thus forming pericardial effusion. This depends on the etiology and is further divided into serous, hemorrhagic and purulent. The pericardial cavity usually contains 15-50 ml of plasma ultrafiltrate in healthy individuals. The pericardium holds the hearts; thus, it works properly. Viral infections are the cause of pericarditis, but it can

also be due to bacteria and fungi. The pericardium serves multiple functions. First, it is the anchor of the heart in the thoracic cavity.

Layers of the pericardium:

Outer parietal pericardium: fibrous layer; pain-sensitive layer.

Inner visceral pericardium: collagen and elastin layer; pain insensitive layer.

The parietal layer is well-innervated by mechanoreceptors and is thus pain sensitive.

During inspiration, the intrathoracic pressure falls and is transmitted to cardiac chambers by the pericardial space. As a result, we can observe an augmentation of venous return, pericardium expansion, and accommodation of more blood into the left ventricle.

Relation between the cardiac chamber, great vessels, thoracic cavity and pericardial space:

- The pericardial sac sits within the thoracic cavity, reflecting intrathoracic pressure.
- While the cardiac chambers lie within the confines of the pericardial sac, the pulmonary vein does not.
- The pulmonary vein exists outside the pericardial sac but within the thoracic cavity, which is directly influenced by changes in intrathoracic pressure.
- The SVC is extra pericardial and extra thoracic, so a proper gradient is formed; right-side filling is more common.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Functions of pericardium

Therefore, if there is a thick fibrotic pericardium, the pressure is not transmitted and hence blood flows from the SVC to the RA during inspiration, so the JVC rises with inspiration rather than falling, known as Kussmaul's sign.

- Interventricular dependence: Inspiratory augmentation of RV filling with no change in LV filling causes bowling of the septum from the R to L, impairing left-sided output.
- This results in a slight inspiratory dip in SBP known as pulsus normalis, typically measuring <10 mmHg.
- Pulsus paradoxus or pulsus normalis aggregans (>10 mmHg)

Figure 1: mechanism of pulsus paradoxus

- Accommodating the excess blood in the pericardial sac, expansion is lost in pericardial disease, resulting in diastolic dysfunction.
- Transmural filling pressure = intracavity pressure - intrapericardial pressure.

Variation of diastolic pressure:

In the presence of a normal pericardium and empty pericardial sac, the diastolic pressure of the RV and LV vary during the respiratory cycle independent of each other.

Acute pericarditis

Case of 30 yr male, ECG shows ST elevation,

Blood urea-202 mg\dl, Sr, Creat-10.5 mg\dl

(Other investigations required echocardiography to check for minimal effusion and rule out tamponade).

- Another typical example of pericarditis with:
- Widespread St elevation PR depression.

- Reciprocal ST depression and PR elevation in V1 and aVR.

Trans myocardial filling pressure = intracavitary pressure - intrapericardial pressure.

If intrapericardial pressure increases, filling decreases (diastolic dysfunction)

Transmission: fall in intrathoracic pressure transmitted to the cardiac chambers.

Rock-like pericardium: no transmission of pressures.

During inspiration, the SVC cannot empty properly into the RA, resulting in elevated JVP (Kussmaul's sign), which is also seen in restrictive cardiomyopathy and tricuspid stenosis.

Systole is normal.

Intrapericardial pressure continues to increase, and eventually, elevation and equalization of diastolic pressure occurs in the post 1/3rd part of diastole (pericardium and the 4 chambers of hearts will have the same pressure).

Phase	JVP	Constrictive pericarditis
Atrial contraction	'a' wave	NORMAL
Atrial relaxation	'x' descent	NORMAL
Atrial filling	'v' wave	NORMAL
Atrial Emptying	'y' descent	SHARP PROMINENT Y DESCENT

Table 1. Relationship of heart cycles with JVP filling

Atrial filling occurs during systole

In diastole, ventricular filling occurs only in the 1st 1/3rd part

Later, no filling occurs.

Ventricular pressure plot:

1. Early dip in diastolic pressure due to isovolumetric relaxation.
2. Rapid filling of the 1st 1/3rd diastole increases the pressure.
3. Pericardial knock (early diastolic)
4. Plateau phase due to rigid and thickened pericardium abruptly halting filling.

RESULTS

Diastolic dysfunction ---> RAP increases ---> increased venous pressure (ascites, edema, JVP, hepatomegaly)

The patient presented with features of right heart failure.

Chronically ill patient with muscle wasting and cachexia (as in cirrhosis of liver)

Ascites is the first feature to develop (ascitic precoc)

MRI (diagnostic): rigid, thickened, calcified pericardium,

Doppler: Exaggerated tricuspid valve inflow velocity (inspiration) and mitral valve inflow velocity (expiration).

Epidemiology

The clinical representation of acute myocarditis in adults is variable, ranging from subclinical to chronic heart failure. If the infection cause is viral, this includes fever, rashes, fatigue, GI and respiratory symptoms. Patients may feel fatigue, palpitations, less working out tolerance or syncope. Chest pain can mimic typical angina and show changes in ECG, such as ST-segment elevation. There is also a chance of CAV occurring in patients with myocarditis.

However, in the case of pericarditis, chest pain is mostly seen. Patients with sudden onset typically present with severe heart failure symptoms, leading to cardiogenic shock.

Clinical representation in children changes according to age. Symptoms such as anxiousness, fever, reduced appetite, tachypnea and cyanosis can be seen in infants. Children above age 2 also have symptoms such as chest pain, abdominal pain, and edema. Here, severity depends on the age of the children, that is, if age is less, there is a greater chance of being affected by chronic diseases. Children need more support at the early stage of the disease.

Acute pericarditis is one of the most common forms of pericardial disease. This can cause chest pain. This is associated with trauma in uremic patients and malignant

diseases. It is more common in men. [1] People with pericarditis can also suffer from chest pain, which usually worsens when taking a deep breath.

Risk factors

Risk factors for myocarditis are not entirely known. Some factors, such as malnutrition, pregnancy, and sex hormones, have been shown. We should also be careful about selenium deficiency, vitamin E deficiency, and other increases in viral virulence. Viral factors, including genome phenotypes, have been shown. Pericarditis occurs in people of all ages. However, primarily men aged 20 to 50 are at higher risk than others. This disease can affect us again even if we get treated this once. This happens to approximately 15% to 30% of people who had this condition before. Sometimes a small number of people may develop chronic pericarditis due to this.

Etiology

INFECTIOUS

Infectious and noninfectious myocarditis. The most common cause is viral infections.

- VIRUS:** The viruses frequently identified are adenovirus and enterovirus, including coxsackie virus. Recently, EMB samples were used to detect viral genomes such as parvovirus B-19 and human herpesvirus-6. Some studies have found that they can be a chance of hepatitis C virus. Other myocarditis-associated viruses include cytomegalovirus, herpes simplex virus, and Epstein–Barr virus. [2]

- BACTERIA:** Bacteria that cause notorious myocarditis can include Salmonella and Shigella. Streptococci, clostridium, tuberculosis, legionellae.

- PARASITES:** trichinosis, schistosomiasis.

- PROTOZOA:** Trypanosoma curisi, toxoplasmosis gondii.

- SPIROCHETES:** borrelia burgdorferi. [5]

NON-INFECTIOUS CAUSES: This includes many causes, such as eosinophilic myocarditis, collagen vascular disease (systemic lupus erythematosus, polymyositis[3])

Major cause of pericardial diaseese can be:

1. INFECTIONS: viral, tubercular
2. NEOPLASM: metastatic – lung of breast cancer, Hodgkin disease, leukemia, melanoma
3. CARDIAC: Early infarction pericarditis
4. AUTOIMMUNE:
5. DRUGS
6. METABOLIC

Causes for pericarditis can also be:

- Postviral pericarditis (most common), coxsackievirus infection, HIV, TB
- Post MI. (aspirin needs to be increased)
- Uremia
- Post-traumatic
- Drugs such as procainamide\hydralazine\minoxidil
- Tumors such as mesotheliomas, small cell lung ca
- Autoimmune conditions SLE, Sjogren's, LgG4.

Pericardial friction rub

- Inflammation of the pericardial sac with or without fluid.
- Very high pitched
- Leathery
- Scratchy in nature
- Seem close to the scar
- Auscultated best with the patient leaning forward or knee- chest position.
- Holding their breath after forced expiration.

Figure 2: pericarditis ECG stages
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At 4 to 6 weeks:

Figure 3: Electrical alternans: Acute pericarditis progressed to cardiac tamponade.

Spodick sign: Significant TP segment depression.

Figure 4: Spodick sign

Figure 5: Acute pericarditis with significant effusion: water bottle configuration

DISCUSSION

Pathology

Myocarditis is an inflammatory cardiomyopathy. This process is initiated after the entry of the virus into myocardial cells. This activates the innate immune response and thus the adaptive immune response over the next week. Pathogenesis was divided into 3 phases. It is classified based on clinical observations and animal model data.

ACUTE INFECTIOUS PHASE

Here, the first phase lasts from 1 to 7 days, including acute cardiac cell damage, host protein exposure and innate immune activation.

Myocardial injury can vary on the basis of the causative agent: adenovirus and enterovirus.

Through the transmembrane, the cytolytic virus enters myocytes and causes severe cytopathic effects by various processes, including viral protease 2A, which mediates the host protein dystrophin [5].

Finally, for other viruses, including influenza virus, the direct cause of myocarditis here is the self-reactive T-cell response by molecular mimicry between viral and cardiac antigens. [3]

The innate immune system eradicates viral infection, but a more persistent response causes tissue damage.

SUBACUTE IMMUNE PHASE

The second phase lasts from 1-4 weeks. Disease is shown by an adaptive T-cell-mediated immune response. The effects of both CD4+ and CD8 cells have been determined, and there are only limited data available for the pathogen genesis of B cells in viral myocarditis. [3]

RECOVERY PHASE

Eviction pathogens from the myocardium usually obtain cardiac function without residual injury. However, the persistent myocardial infection breakdown of T-cell tolerance leads to chronic inflammation.

Diagnosis: uremic pericarditis

Sitting up and leaning forward relieved sharp chest pain, stabbing, and pleuritic pain.

On auscultation pericardial friction rub,

ECG shows global ST elevation followed by diffusion.

Frequent PR segment depression

No reciprocal inversion

CONCLUSION

Treatment

There are minimal data for the treatment of myopericarditis. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs can be given if there is more pericarditis illness in left ventricular function. However, in the case of myocardial function, we suggest NSAIDs, which worsen myocardial function. Therefore, the minimum dose is used for relief, which is symptomatic. Therefore, if the patient has signs and symptoms of heart failure with the chance of myocardial involvement, standard heart failure therapy with the help of beta blockers, angiotensin-converting enzymes, and diuretics should be administered. Colchicine is used daily in patients with pericarditis. However, this has no role in myocarditis.[13]

Other treatments include the following:

- Antibiotics
- Antiviral interferon A
- Oral therapy with ACE inhibitors
- Digoxin
- Oxygen therapy
- Corticosteroids and immunosuppressants

Prophylaxis

There is no prevention of myocarditis. However, staying distant from people with flu symptoms and other respiratory infections might help.

REFERENCES

- [1] Imazio M. Noninfectious pericarditis: management challenges for cardiologists. *Kardiol Pol.* 2020 May 25;78(5):396-403. [PubMed] [Reference list]
- [2]<https://rarediseases.info.nih.gov/diseases/7137/myocarditis>
- [3]<https://rarediseases.info.nih.gov/diseases/7137/myocarditis>

[4] <https://www.statpearls.com/articlelibrary/viewarticle/17161>

[5] Dababneh E, Siddique MS. Pericarditis. 2022 Aug 8. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan–. PMID: 28613734.

[6] Hoit BD. Anatomy and Physiology of the Pericardium. *Cardiol Clin*. 2017 Nov;35(4):481-490. - [PubMed](#)

[7] Little WC, Freeman GL. Pericardial disease. *Circulation*. 2006 Mar 28;113(12):1622-32. - [PubMed](#)

[8] Imazio M, Gaita F, LeWinter M. Evaluation and Treatment of Pericarditis: A Systematic Review. *JAMA*. 2015 Oct 13;314(14):1498-506. - [PubMed](#)

[9] Spodick DH. Acute cardiac tamponade. *N Engl J Med*. 2003 Aug 14;349(7):684-90. - [PubMed](#)

[10] Imazio M, Lazaros G, Brucato A, Gaita F. Recurrent pericarditis: new and emerging therapeutic options. *Nat Rev Cardiol*. 2016 Feb;13(2):99-105. - [PubMed](#)

[11] Sagar S, Liu PP, Cooper LT Jr. Myocarditis. *Lancet*. 2012 Feb 25;379(9817):738-47. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(11)60648-X. Epub 2011 Dec 18. PMID: 22185868; PMCID: PMC5814111.

12. Shodiyeva, D., Bobakandova, M., Annaev, M., & Tokhirova, J. (2023). IDENTIFICATION AND ISOLATION OF ENDOPHYTIC FUNGI PRODUCING L-ASPARAGINASE IN REPRESENTATIVES OF THE ASTERATCEA FAMILY. *Science and innovation*, 2(D2), 107-112.

13. Annayev, M., Shodiyeva, D., & Annayev, M. (2023). BACILLUS SAFENSIS BAKTERIYA SHTAMLARINING BIOTEXNOLOGIK POTENSIALINI BAHOLASH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(7), 25-30.